

Development of zirconia porcelain in presence of active silica and its characterization

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Zirconia containing body having a lower maturing temperature and superior thermo-mechanical properties were developed. Replacement of quartz by precipitated active silica reduced the maturing temperature of triaxial porcelain. 15% ZrO₂ was found to be optimum for improving mechanical strength and other properties.

Zircon porcelain is exceptionally mechanically strong, has good electrical characteristics and very good thermal shock resistance and it has got several advantages¹. Pask and Tomsia² postulated that the heating rate is crucial to the crystal structure of mullite. Tai *et al.*³ followed a new approach of preparation of anorthite porcelain bodies using non-plastic materials. Pham-Gia *et al.*⁴ noted that by increasing the degree of cross linking in the glaze structure, it is possible to improve the mechanical abrasion resistance of porcelain glazes. The SiO₂ content in the batch has the greatest influence on abrasion resistance. Addition of ZrSiO₄ is also beneficial. The objective of the present investigation was to compile a suitable composition of Zircon porcelain, which can be matured at a comparatively low temperature.

Table 1. Chemical analysis of the raw materials

Constituents	Percent present in			
	China clay	Precipitated silica	Feldspar	Zircon
SiO ₂	45.30	98.50	59.67	30.01
Al ₂ O ₃	38.38	Nil	18.21	0.90
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.30	Nil	0.30	0.11
TiO ₂	1.44	Nil	Nil	0.26
MgO	0.25	Nil	Nil	0.22
CaO	0.05	Nil	Nil	0.14
Na ₂ O	0.27	Nil	2.30	Nil
K ₂ O	0.04	Nil	11.52	Nil
ZrO ₂	Nil	Nil	Nil	66.34
Loss on ignition	13.97	1.50	Nil	Nil

Results and discussion

The compositions (Table 2) were selected such that flint in the ideal triaxial system was replaced by precipitated SiO₂, which possessed very high surface area of the order of 250 m² g⁻¹. In other batches SiO₂ was substituted by Zircon. Amongst the impurities in the raw material TiO₂ was very much significant as present in china clay which generally promotes mullitisation in the alumino silicate system. The over all analysis (Table 1) indicated that the raw materials were suitable for manufacturing white ware body.

Table 2. Batch composition

Batch no.	China clay (%)	Precipitated silica (%)	Feldspar (%)	Zircon (%)
I	50	25	25	Nil
II	50	20	25	5
III	50	15	25	10
IV	50	10	25	15

The firing temperature was selected in the lower range because of greater reactivity of precipitated SiO₂ compared to quartz and dissolution of Zircon resulting a liquid phase in presence of basic impurities. The first manifestation of firing effect in a triaxial body was shrinkage as shown in Fig 1. The nature of the curve indicated the identical mechanism of interaction of the raw materials. With the increase of Zircon content, the curves approached to linear nature, which was related to the dissociation of Zircon.

With the increase of temperature, the apparent poro-

Fig. 1. Variation of linear shrinkage (%) with temperature (°C) : (o) Batch I, (●) Batch II, (x) Batch III and (Δ) Batch IV.

Fig. 2. Variation of apparent porosity (%) with temperature (°C) : (o) Batch I, (●) Batch II, (x) Batch III and (Δ) Batch IV.

sity decreased as observed in the Fig. 2. The nature of the curve belonged to that of sigmoid type, which might be due to the fact that porosity reduction was contributed by poor filling by glassy phase and particle drag due to

secondary crystallization. Minimum porosity achieved was 0.24% at 1350° with highest Zircon content up to 15% following which it decreased again.

Nature of the phase transformation in a semivitreous body is often identified by the true density measurement. The overall density is an average of the different phases present. The results are given in Table 3. In all compositions except Batch I, maximum density value was achieved at 1300° following which it decreased due to dissolution of some high density phases by the liquid melt. True density values at all temperatures followed direct relationship with ZrO₂ in the composition.

Table 3. Relationship between true density and firing temperature of the different batches

Batch no.	True density (g cm ⁻³) after firing at (°C)			
	1200	1250	1300	1350
I	2.30	2.33	2.37	2.38
II	2.36	2.37	2.50	2.42
III	2.39	2.41	2.55	2.48
IV	2.41	2.48	2.58	2.52

The mechanical strength of a semivitreous body is important when its applications are considered. It was determined by three point bending method and the results are given in Table 4. Regarding the effect of ZrO₂, strength gradually increased and maximum strength was achieved at 1300° and then decreases which might be associated with the grain boundary dissolution.

Table 4. Relationship between flexural strength (kg cm⁻²) and firing temperature and different batch compositions

Batch no.	Flexural strength (kg cm ⁻²) after firing at (°C)			
	1200	1250	1300	1350
I	205	229	177	131
II	183	233	248	196
III	230	256	272	208
IV	220	260	280	187

Considering the above results 1300° was found to be optimum for such type of body mixture and as such XRD analysis (Figs. not shown) of the 1300° fired samples were carried out.

The major phase identified in all the compositions was mullite, the most stable phase in the alumino silicate system and the minor phase was cristobalite. ZrO₂ phases were not identified which may be due to formation of some glassy zirconate phases.

For examining the microstructure, SEM analysis (Figs.

not shown) was performed with 1300° fired samples. In the Batch III composition, distinct cross-linked needles were visible. The grain boundaries were sharp. Micro size ZrO₂ grains were visible in irregular fashion and were mostly intergranular.

Conclusion :

- (1) Replacement of quartz by precipitated silica activates the process of interaction and reduces the maturing temperature of triaxial porcelain.
- (2) Incorporation of ZrO₂ in this system improves the mechanical strength and other properties. 15% ZrO₂ was found to be optimum.
- (3) The maximum amount of dissociated ZrO₂ went into glassy phase and distribution was not homogeneous.

Experimental

The required quantities of the raw materials viz., china clay, precipitated silica, feldspar, and zircon were weighed separately, taken in a pot mill and milled for 16 h under wet condition. After milling the slip was evaporated to dryness and ready for fabrication.

Rectangular bars and cubes were fabricated by semi-

dry pressing in a hydraulic press at a pressure of 1500 kg cm⁻². After thorough drying they were fired at 1200°, 1250°, 1300° and 1350° respectively, in a muffle furnace. The heating rate was 5°/min up to 600° followed by 10°/min up to final temperature. The soaking time was 1½ h.

The fired properties such as linear shrinkage, apparent porosity, and true density were tested by following the conventional methods.

XRD analysis was carried out using a Philips Per (1790) X-ray diffractometer with scanning speed 2° (2θ)/min using CuK_α radiation 1.5405600 Å (λ). Scanning electron micrographic analysis was performed in a Hitachi-S-530 operated at 5 kV.

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